

Early Galaxies and Elastons.

Valeriy P. Polulyakh

Abstract.

The Big Bang is the basis of cosmology, and the presence of DM and DE, which are not detected in observations, is important. The main postulate of BB: instantaneous appearance of space, matter and energy. Based on this, models of the formation of stars and galaxies were obtained. Why everything appeared at this particular moment, and not at some other time, is unclear. Recent observations with the Webb Telescope indicate serious shortcomings of these models, in particular the inability to explain the unusually rapid emergence of formed galaxies. Here we show that instead of instantaneous birth, the Universe undergoes an evolutionary development from chaotic space to metric space, when stable formations of elastons appear, possessing elastic energy and giving birth to stars, galaxies, and volumes of flat space, bypassing the singularity. This model avoids many of the problems faced by the Big Bang. Clouds of gas and dust are the by-product, not the cause, of the evolution of space objects. There are two types of boundaries available in our model, and both have very important physical functions. The first type of boundaries separating elastons from Euclidean space, which becomes ideal for fulfilling conservation laws. The second type of boundaries - the boundary between Euclidean and external non-metrizable space is a thermalizer serving as a source of CMBR.

Introduction.

Λ CDM model is a mathematical model of the Big Bang theory. One of the key ingredients of the standard Λ CDM Concordance model of the universe is Cold Dark matter which constitutes about 25% of the total mass-energy budget. However, there is no laboratory evidence for any cold dark matter candidate. We even do not know whether CDM particle is a fermion or boson. Λ CDM has no explicit physical theory for the origin or physical nature of dark matter or dark energy.

The Λ CDM model has to satisfy the cosmological principle, which states that, on a large-enough scale, the universe looks the same in all directions (isotropy) and from every location (homogeneity). However, recent findings have suggested that violations of the cosmological principle, especially of isotropy, exist. These violations have called the Λ CDM model into question, with some authors suggesting that the cosmological principle is obsolete or that the Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker metric breaks down in the late universe.

Large spatial inhomogeneities in the distribution of superclusters and voids on scales of 200-300 Mpc and above, and as observed by the HST, are potentially inconsistent with the standard model. [1]

Independent observables, based on different physics, are tracking the CMB dipole direction suggests that the Universe is anisotropic in the direction of the CMB dipole.

Recent observations from the James Webb Space Telescope have identified a population of massive galaxy sources ($> 10^{10} M_{\odot}$) at $z > 7 - 10$, formed less than 700 Myr after the Big Bang. Such massive galaxies do not have enough time to form within Λ CDM model, and hence these observations significantly challenge standard cosmology. [2]

This early galaxy formation faster than expected poses a radically new challenge to Λ CDM. Existence of surprisingly massive galaxies in the early universe challenges the preferred models describing how dark matter halos drive galaxy formation.

Observations from the James Webb Space Telescope [3] have resulted in various galaxies confirmed by spectroscopy at high redshift, such as JADES-GS-z13-0 at cosmological redshift of 13.2. Other candidate galaxies which have not been confirmed by spectroscopy include CEERS-93316 at cosmological redshift of 16.4. Such massive sources so early in cosmic history would be difficult to reconcile with the expectation from standard Λ CDM.

Distant galaxies also contain heavy elements (heavier than helium) not consistent with theory.

A solution to the problem is being sought in two directions: with the help of spectroscopic measurements, they are trying to reduce z of the observed galaxies and improve the Lambda theory (but DM and DE have not been found). At the same time, the basic idea of cosmology, the instantaneous birth of the Universe (Big Bang), is retained. In work [4] the problem of early galaxies was predicted. Some cosmologists believe that the Λ CDM model may be superseded by a different, yet unknown cosmological model. This work is devoted to the study of another possibility - the evolutionary development of space.

In article [5] an attempt is made to paint a picture of the evolution from chaos to flat physical space. It is not known whether this evolution was a consequence of certain general laws above physics or whether it was the result of an endless chaotic process. But as a result, a world appeared with an algorithm of behavior. This algorithm is the following statement: For the world not to be chaotic, it must have a COORDINATED SET OF PHYSICAL LAWS. If this condition is met, then the world becomes stable and evolves considering this set of laws.

As a rule, the cosmological models are constructed based on the theory of gravity. It makes sense since the behavior of space-occupying matter is of the greatest interest. But where do this matter and space come from? It seems there is a missing link between cosmic structure and gravity. The structure and evolution of space are the central problems of physical cosmology. What is a physical space (PS)?

Newton: "Although space may be empty of body, nevertheless it is not itself a void and something is there because spaces are there, though nothing more than that."

William Clifford: "That this variation of the curvature of space is what really happens in that phenomenon which we call the *motion of matter*, whether ponderable or ethereal."

P. Drude: "The conception of ether absolutely at rest is the most simple and the most natural - at least if the ether is conceived to be not a substance but merely space endowed with certain physical properties. "

P. Dirac claimed: "... with the new theory of electrodynamics we are rather forced to have an aether".

It is sometimes said that PS is represented by quantum foam consisting of virtual particles, which are nevertheless considered to be material bodies. But it is known that a reference system cannot be associated with material bodies or “foam” because it would be “absolute”. Our interest is not referential space but background one, so we treat PS (but not the time) as an entity. It is very important for us to explain the increase of the global volume of the universe without stretching of the local space.

What is the difference between Euclidean flat space and Einsteinian flat space? For Euclidean and Newtonian space, the flatness was a natural condition of milieu but for Einsteinian one to be flat we need unseen dark matter and dark energy.

The elastons and evolution of space.

The central idea of a new paradigm is an existence of a certain entity – the elaston, which can give rise to the physical Euclidean space, matter, and energy all the way along its evolution. There are no spatial singularities.

There is the question in any cosmological model: “Why, after an infinity of nonexistence, was the World generated, at one moment rather than another?” In this model the answer is simple; the existence of our World is only a moment in the perpetual evolution of space. The elaston emerges as a link in the infinite transmutation of space so it is not a peculiar *moment* in cosmic time. Two conceptions lie in the foundation of elastonic hypothesis:

1. An existence of specific elasticity as a property of space.
2. A concentration of the finite elastic energy of space in the form of soliton-like entities – elastons which are a domain of "compressed" space. The energy density of elastic space is $c^4 R / 8\pi G$ where R is a scalar curvature. The compressed space relaxes into Euclidean space that is filled up with particles in accordance with equation (1). It is natural to consider as a boundary the distance where the density of elastic energy drops to the nuclear one: $\rho_{\text{nucl}} \sim 10^{14} \text{ g/sm}^3$.

Under soliton we comprehend here a long living spatial formation protecting its shape against spreading. Clifford's idea of representation of matter as a space curvature was rejected from the very outset. The matter is considered as a by-product of evolution of space however the energy of elastons is described in the geometrical manner through metrical properties of space. So elaston is not the matter, in the sense of particles, but it is pre-matter that can give birth to particles. Though our surrounding or milieu we call "physical space" the space inside the elaston is also real but we call it "elastonic space". We will act in the following way – using our understanding of reality try to find promising mathematical resources and as Dirac recommended “...try to interpret the new mathematical features in terms of physical entities...” At the same time, we must endeavor not move away from the physical reality. New mathematical tool we have chosen for our model is a Ricci flow technique. We must start with non-metrizable space.

The fact is that we have no intuition about non-metrizable spaces. We do not even have physical language to discuss such a reality. Only thing we can do is to use mathematical terminology relying on the hope that in the future we could develop suitable physical comprehension.

In the beginning of the chain, we can put so-called pathological space that is non-metrizable. A domain of well-behaved space arises as a result of self-perfection. Well-behaving is a continuous process, one can have space with better and better behavior. On this stage the space does not have any geometry. It is analogous to antichain where any two elements are incomparable. Well-behaved domain evolves into space that is second countable. If for all this the points of the space can be separated by neighborhood then evolution has led to metrizability of space. Our chain may now have a form:

Pathological space → Domain of well-behaved space → Second-countable space → General Riemannian space → Ricci flow → Elaston → Particles + Euclidean space

We consider in our world the presence of two physically distinctive areas: 1) standard physical space with particles, gravity, and other physical fields, 2) “compressed” space with non-zero “elastic” energy and lack of particles. At the expense of “elastic” energy the mass (dm) and physical space volume (dV) can be created. Our hypothesis is proportionality between dm/dt and dV/dt :

$$\Pi \frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where Π is a coefficient proportionality that have dimension [m^3/kg], or

$$\Pi \frac{d\rho}{dt} = \text{div } \mathbf{v}. \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{v} is velocity of PS. There is no dragging force applied to the stationary moving matter from the PS which possess properties of perfect fluid:

- a) The PS has zero viscosity
- b) There is no heat transfer in the PS flow
- c) The motion of PS is always potential, so

$$\text{curl } \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad \mathbf{v} = -\text{grad } \varphi \quad (3)$$

where φ is the velocity potential.

To make flat space we need a phase transition on the boundary. The elastic energy is the free energy that produces particles and transforms into the rest mass energy. The Euclidean space is a background vacuum state in contrast to the elaston that is an upper metastable state of 3-space. After this phase transition from elaston to vacuum state, the space becomes a flat passive stage in the Newtonian sense. As a result, the geometry acquires the most symmetrical space and physics gains particles and physical fields acting between them. After this the Ricci flow is unable to change the geometry of space. The flatness of our space is a consequence of this inability. The creation of particles which utilize the former elastic energy is an essential process to protect the energy conservation. Contrary to the cornerstone idea of GR the space becomes Euclidean in the presence of matter. The Ricci flow is a second order nonlinear parabolic differential evolution equation like the heat or diffusion equations

$$\frac{dg(t)}{dt} = -2\text{Ric}g(t) \quad (4)$$

where $g(t)$ is a metric, $\text{Ric } g(t)$ is a tensor Ricci. The minus sign is because a plus one leads to backwards heat-type equation, which has no solution in general. The Ricci flow is the process which deforms given metric with variable Ricci curvature to even out of all the bumps and hollows in a

manner formally analogous to diffusion or heat. The metric shrinks in positive Ricci curvature while it expands in the negative Ricci curvature direction.

Uniformization and geometrization are working together since for geometrization we need smooth space but smoothing implies geometry. There is no contradiction since geometrization here is regarded as Klein's conception of constant curvature that is characterized by its own group of isometries. General Riemannian geometry which includes spaces of variable curvature is much broader. The uniformization takes place on general Riemannian geometry and, only after the curvature of each decomposed homogeneous space becomes constant, space acquires geometry in Klein's meaning that is Thurston's geometrization. Does elaston have geometry? The answer is: *no* in the Klein's meaning and *yes* in the general Riemannian sense.

The evolution equation of the Ricci curvature has form

$$dR_{ij}/dt = \Delta R_{ij} + Q_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where Δ is the Laplace-Beltrami operator, Q involves quadratic expressions in the curvature. This is a nonlinear heat-type equation. Analysis shows [6] that the Ricci flow preserves positive Ricci curvature in dimension 3 that is not a case for dimensions > 3 . The Ricci flow does not preserve negative Ricci curvature in dimensions > 2 . On the other hand, the Ricci flow "geometrizes" 3-space of positive curvature. This analysis shows that the Ricci flow tends to favor positive curvature and even more, elastons ($Ric > 0$) acquire a naturalness of existence only in 3-space. The dimension 3 of our physical space probably follows from this conclusion.

Sun-Chin Chu show [7] that spherically symmetric metric on 3-space is being a gradient Ricci soliton which positive curvature must be open like paraboloid. Scalar curvature has its maximum at the origin and falls off like $1/s$.

In general, there are directions of positive and negative $Ric(g)$ and metric may contract or expand. For dumbbell metric, for example, the neck may shrink since a positive curvature in S^2 direction will dominate [8]. After the neck is pinched off a topological decomposition into pieces happens. In [9] "corseting sphere" S^3 is numerically examined. A critical value of the corseting parameter was found. For small amount of corseting Ricci flow converges to the round sphere metric, while for a large amount of corseting a neck pinch singularity occurs. A pinching, probably, will happen also for the entity with more than one neck – multi-decomposition.

Here are two important corollaries for our model:

- a. Ricci solitons, which are forming by evolution of Ricci flow, may be used as a mathematical description of elastons.
- b. The elaston under supercritical regime may to experience neck pinch formation and decomposition of elaston may occur.

It can be assumed that the energy of elastons that cascades down during decomposition leads to the birth of stars.

Let us go back to physical space. We live in a finite World with a simply connected topology. Our World globally has composite geometry. It is a 3-ball that has Euclidean metric with immersed elastons that have non-Euclidean "compressed" metric. Euclidean space has a final geometry that is not liable more to the action of Ricci flow. An increase of Euclidean volume is the reason of expanding of our World. The elastons are mills for generation of new entities and Euclidean space is a calm zone for placid evolution of matter. This space differs from Newtonian global space which is too immovable and from Cartesian space that is too mobile. We make difference between space (stage) and particles (players) though in our

comprehension a real Euclidean space exists (as a whole) only together with particles. This is not a relationism but **coexistence**. Here the stage and players come into being together: Euclidean space and particles cannot exist independently. Particles are the by-product of evolution of space. An evolution of the elastic space which was possessed the energy results in creation of final energetically passive but highly symmetrical flat space and the particles that reserve for themselves the former elastic energy.

We can look at the evolution of space from standpoint of the entropy. The evolution is bounded up with a change of the entropy. But change of the entropy is connected with a presence of coarse-graining structures. The fine-graining structures or uniform media conserve the entropy and so, not support evolution. It is precisely this fact that explains why our World had started in elastonic form. The elastons have high level of organization, minimal entropy S , minimal volume V and maximum reserve of free energy F , which is converting into the energy of the particles. At that, the new born Euclidean space itself has zero free energy. The Euclidean space is a ground state of the space condition. From the energy point of view the evolution of the space looks like following: free energy of space is diminishing $dG/dt < 0$, volume is increasing, $dV/dt > 0$. This means that evolution of our World is feeding by the free energy of elastons and is still elapsing at this epoch, as against to the Big Bang model where some instantaneous process happened long time ago and the results of which we are observing till now. New diverse structures emerge owing to the elastic energy of elastons. Our World is an open system that creates its order at the expense of the free energy leaking from elastons. This can happen only since the whole system of Euclidean section of space and elastons are far away from thermodynamic equilibrium.

The coarse-graining requires the presence of the boundaries. Just existing of the boundary of space evokes the sacred horror among the present-day cosmologists. They are trying somehow to twist the space so that any boundaries vanish. Of course, there are in mathematics some beautiful objects, for instance hypersphere or 3-sphere, without boundary but it is unlikely that something similar exists in our physical world. Sometimes it is said that Euclidean flat space can exist in two ways: infinite unbounded space or finite unbounded one in the form of flat 3-torus, but there is no any observational support for these models. Often the Cosmological principle or the Copernican principle is proposed to negate the boundary existence. But the Cosmological principle is not a law of nature; most probable it is a matter of belief.

There two sorts of boundaries are available in our model and both are endowed with greatly important physical functions. We mentioned already the first kind of boundaries that separate elastons from Euclidean space which becomes ideal for fulfilling the laws of conservation. This is the arena for COORDINATED SET OF PHYSICAL LAWS. The second kind of boundaries is a border between Euclidean and external non-metrizable space.

Any photon incident upon this boundary may experience three different outcomes: reflection, transmission, and absorption. A reflection is ruled out since there is no reflector. A transmission is not permitted because the space from the opposite side of the boundary is non-metric. The only possibility is an absorption being independent of frequency of the incident photon. This is exactly the property of the black body. The absorbed energy heats boundary to some effective temperature T that determines the temperature of the CMBR. So, the boundary of our World is the source of the CMBR. An observational equality of the CMBR energy density and the star radiation energy, otherwise mysterious, supports this model. The energy density of diffuse starlight in the universe is $\rho \sim 10^{-13}$ erg cm⁻³. This boundary is a skin layer for the incident electromagnetic radiation. The incident energy flow is $\rho \cdot c$ (erg cm⁻² sec⁻¹). If boundary under

this flow of the energy acquires the temperature T then the blackbody radiation in accordance with Stefan - Boltzmann law is $j = \sigma T^4$. The balance of the energy is

$$\sigma T^4 = \rho \cdot c \quad (6)$$

and

$$T = \sqrt[4]{\frac{\rho c}{\sigma}} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{10^{-13} \cdot 3 \cdot 10^{10}}{5.7 \cdot 10^{-5}}} = 2.7 \text{ K} \quad (7)$$

So, the boundary acquires under the star light flow the temperature equal to the CMB temperature. It is hardly accidental coincidence.

This boundary is a skin layer for the incident electromagnetic radiation. It works like radiation thermalizer. Mathematically this boundary has properties both closed and open manifold. One section of space can be flat and others are curved. A metric space is trivially a gauge space and hence there exist some conservation laws of physical entities. In our model the space on the outside of the elastons is always immutable Euclidean but not immovable like Newtonian space. The mutability of the space takes place only inside and on the boundary of elastons. The immutability of the final Euclidean space is a consequence of the property of the Ricci flow that has no effect on the flat space. The new born space that is determined by dV/dt locally is the absolute space in the Newtonian meaning, except for “immovability”. That is the Newtonian space serves as the sections of the Cartesian “hydrodynamic” space.

Applications of the Model.

This list contains information about some of the applications and implications of this model.

In work [10] the mechanism of formation of jets and outflow of matter from cosmic objects: stars and galaxies is considered.

Paper [4] presents considerations on the origin of galaxies and their clusters.

Article [11] discusses the mechanism of evolution of space objects.

Article [12] proposes a new mechanism for star formation.

Work [13] questions the existence of BHs and DMs in our galaxy and provides a possible solution to the observations.

The work [14] proposes a mechanism for the formation of a large-scale structure of space.

Article [15] questions the existence of DM and DE not found in observations.

Article [16] proposes a mechanism for the formation of galactic structures: Bubbles, Supershells, Fountains and Winds

In work [17] an attempt is made to explain the existence of supermassive stars.

In work [18] a mechanism for the formation of asymmetry of the baryon number of particles and antiparticles in the universe is proposed.

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